

*Melenko Svitlana Romanivna**Associate Professor of the Department, Candidate of Medical Sciences**Associate Professor of the Higher Education Institution**Department of Infectious Diseases and Epidemiology**Stan Lenutsa**Roman Kuzhnyi**Students, specialty "medicine 222"**Bukovyna State Medical University**Chernivtsi, Ukraine*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15569705>

NEW APPROACHES TO VACCINATION: PROSPECTS OF mRNA VACCINES IN FIGHTING INFECTIONS (LITERATURE REVIEW)

Abstract

Since Edward Jenner's first successful vaccination studies in the late 1700s, vaccine development and large-scale immunization campaigns have been the societal response to infectious disease outbreaks around the world. The global search for a vaccine against SARS-CoV-2 has introduced an entirely new class of vaccine products: at least three of the candidates at the forefront of the vaccine race are messenger RNA (mRNA) nanoparticles. Vaccination is one of the most effective methods of combating infectious diseases. In recent years, mRNA vaccines have become a revolutionary technology in this field. They have demonstrated high efficacy in combating COVID-19 and have opened up new possibilities for the prevention of other infectious diseases [1,2].

Keywords: vaccination, mRNA vaccines, infectious diseases, immunogenicity, prevention.

Relevance of the topic: Traditional vaccines based on inactivated or attenuated viruses have their limitations, in particular in terms of production speed, virus mutations, and possible side effects. mRNA vaccines provide rapid development, high efficacy, and adaptability to new strains of infections. Their use can be key in the fight against not only COVID-19 but also other viral infections, such as influenza, HIV, Zika virus, etc. Vaccines consist of strands of mRNA packaged in a neutrally charged lipid-based nanoparticle. The speed with which these novel therapeutics have reached phase III clinical trials is remarkable, especially because they were the first mRNA-based therapeutics to receive FDA and EMA approval [1,2,3].

The aim of the study: To analyze the current status and prospects of mRNA vaccines for the prevention of viral infections.

Materials and Methods: Analysis of the current literature, including reviews, meta-analyses and clinical trials published in leading medical databases (PubMed, Scopus) over the past 5 years, as well as information from WHO, CDC and pharmaceutical companies on the efficacy and safety of mRNA vaccines.

Results and discussion:

The concept of mRNA vaccines dates back to the 1990s, when scientists began to explore the possibility of using synthetic mRNA molecules to induce immune responses. However, at that time, there were significant technical obstacles, including the instability of mRNA and problems with its delivery to cells [1].

A breakthrough occurred in 2005, when Karikó and Weissman discovered a method of modifying nucleotides in mRNA, which reduced the immunogenicity of the molecule itself and increased its stability. In the 2010s, Moderna and BioNTech began active testing of mRNA vaccines, and with the COVID-19 pandemic, this technology has gained worldwide recognition. [1,2].

All mRNA vaccines target the same SARS-CoV-2 antigen and include mRNA encoding the full-length transmembrane S-protein. The genetic sequence has been slightly modified to stabilize the conformation of the pre-fusion glycoprotein by two proline (2P) substitutions (mutations K986P and V987P). The main advantage of the mRNA approach is that proteins are produced by host cells, as would be the case in the case of natural virus infection[3]. As a result, the proteins produced will undergo the same post-translational processing, including glycosylation, subunit cleavage, and proper protein folding. Thus, the S-glycoprotein is eventually incorporated as a trimer into the membrane of mRNA-transfected cells, allowing it to be efficiently exposed in its antigenically native conformation prior to fusion with B cells [4].

Similar to more classical vaccination approaches, COVID-19 mRNA vaccines are injected into the muscle, where they cause localized and transient inflammation that recruits various immune cells to the injection site [5].

COVID-19 mRNA vaccines have mainly focused on triggering B cells to promote the induction of neutralizing antibodies, but there is also good evidence that CD8+ T cell and CD4+ T cell responses may contribute to protection against SARS-CoV-2 [5,6]. Memory T cells, especially those in the upper respiratory tract, can limit the severity of the disease and shorten the duration of the disease by rapidly eliminating infected cells and coordinating antibody production. In patients with COVID-19, coordinated adaptive immunity of CD4+ T cells, CD8+ T cells, and antibody responses correlated with a milder course of the disease, while uncoordinated responses often did not control the disease [7].

The mRNA vaccines containing nucleoside-modified mRNA (BioNTech/Pfizer and Moderna) report a clear dose-dependence in the occurrence of localized and systemic side effects. In addition, side effects were

more common after the booster dose compared to the main dose. According to clinical trials, the effectiveness of mRNA vaccines against COVID-19 (Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna) was more than 90% in preventing the symptomatic course of the disease. However, the effectiveness varied due to virus mutations, which stimulated the development of booster doses [8].

The side effects of mRNA vaccines are mostly mild or moderate: pain at the injection site, temporary fever, headache. Serious reactions, such as myocarditis or anaphylactic reactions, are rare and are investigated by specialists [9].

In addition to COVID-19, mRNA vaccines are being actively studied for other infectious diseases: Influenza - mRNA vaccines allow for annual adaptation of the vaccine composition to the current strains of the virus. HIV - due to the high variability of HIV, traditional vaccines are ineffective, and mRNA technology can provide a more accurate immune response. Zika virus, Ebola, hepatitis C - clinical trials of new mRNA vaccines are ongoing. In cancer, the use of mRNA vaccines to stimulate immunity against tumor cells is being investigated [10].

Conclusion: mRNA vaccines are a promising area in the prevention of infectious diseases, allowing for a rapid response to new challenges. They have a high safety and efficacy profile, and their further development can significantly change the approach to vaccination in the future. However, further research and optimization of production processes are required for the full implementation of mRNA vaccines for the prevention of infectious diseases.

Список літератури.

1. Verbeke, Rein et al. "The dawn of mRNA vaccines: The COVID-19 case." *Journal of controlled release: official journal of the Controlled Release Society* vol. 333 (2021): 511-520. doi: 10.1016/j.jconrel.2021.03.043

2. Teo, Shyh Poh. "Review of COVID-19 mRNA Vaccines: BNT162b2 and mRNA-1273." *Journal of*

pharmacy practice vol. 35,6 (2022): 947-951. doi:10.1177/08971900211009650

3. Munro, Alasdair P S et al. "Safety, immunogenicity, and reactogenicity of BNT162b2 and mRNA-1273 COVID-19 vaccines given as fourth-dose boosters following two doses of ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 or BNT162b2 and a third dose of BNT162b2 (COV-BOOST): a multicentre, blinded, phase 2, randomised trial." *The Lancet. Infectious diseases* vol. 22,8 (2022): 1131-1141. doi:10.1016/S1473-3099(22)00271-7

4. Tumban, Ebenezer. "Lead SARS-CoV-2 Candidate Vaccines: Expectations from Phase III Trials and Recommendations Post-Vaccine Approval." *Viruses* vol. 13,1 54. 31 Dec. 2020, doi:10.3390/v13010054

5. Rosa, Sara Sousa et al. "mRNA vaccines manufacturing: Challenges and bottlenecks." *Vaccine* vol. 39,16 (2021): 2190-2200. doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2021.03.038

6. Yasmin, Farah et al. "Adverse events following COVID-19 mRNA vaccines: A systematic review of cardiovascular complication, thrombosis, and thrombocytopenia." *Immunity, inflammation and disease* vol. 11,3 (2023): e807. doi:10.1002/iid3.807

7. Vishweshwaraiah, Yashavantha L, and Nikolay V Dokholyan. "mRNA vaccines for cancer immunotherapy." *Frontiers in immunology* vol. 13 1029069. 14 Dec. 2022, doi:10.3389/fimmu.2022.1029069

8. Lorentzen, Cathrine Lund et al. "Clinical advances and ongoing trials on mRNA vaccines for cancer treatment." *The Lancet. Oncology* vol. 23,10 (2022): e450-e458. doi:10.1016/S1470-2045(22)00372-2

9. Amanpour, S. "The Rapid Development and Early Success of Covid 19 Vaccines Have Raised Hopes for Accelerating the Cancer Treatment Mechanism." *Archives of Razi Institute* vol. 76,1 (2021): 1-6. doi:10.22092/ari.2021.353761.1612

10. Wei, Jiao, and Ai-Min Hui. "The paradigm shift in treatment from Covid-19 to oncology with mRNA vaccines." *Cancer treatment reviews* vol. 107 (2022): 102405. doi:10.1016/j.ctrv.2022.102405